

Chemical Investigations of the stem-bark of *Eugenia fruticosa* Roxb. and bark of *Eugenia wallichii* Wight III.

S. Ghosh Majumdar and Swapnadip Thakur

The isolation of friedelin, epi-friedelanol and betulinic acid as its methyl ester are common in both the species. But β -sitosterol has been isolated only from the bark of *E. wallichii*.

Eugenia fruticosa and *Eugenia wallichii* (Fam. Myrtaceae) are large and evergreen tree. The former is found all over India while the latter in Sikkim, Khasia, Bhutan and Assam. Investigations were undertaken because of chemotaxonomic interest. However, no chemical studies has yet been reported on these species. *E. fruticosa* was collected locally and *E. wallichii* from Raja Bhat Khawa Forest, North Bengal.

Petroleum extract of the stem-bark of *E. fruticosa* was concentrated, the yellow crystalline material filtered, washed with a little petroleum when a white residue and deep yellow filtrate was obtained. The white residue was separated into ether-soluble and ether-insoluble fractions. The filtrate on evaporation afforded yellow crystalline material.

The ether-soluble fraction on extraction with cold aqueous alkali and subsequent acidification of the alkaline extract resulted in the separation of crystalline triterpene carboxylic acid. This on esterification with diazomethane and on purification by chromatography over de-activated alumina (elution with petroleum-benzene mixture) afforded crystalline white material. This on recrystallisation furnished methyl betulinate, m.p. 218°, $[\alpha]_D + 8.1^\circ$ (CHCl_3). The identity with methyl betulinate has been confirmed through mixed m.p. determination and comparison of its IR spectrum with that of an authentic specimen¹. The IR spectrum (KBr) showed peaks at 2.85 μ ($-\text{OH}$), 5.85 μ (ester $\text{C}=\text{O}$), 6.1 μ ($\text{C}=\text{C}$), 7.25 μ , 7.35 μ (gem-dimethyl group), 8.55 μ ($\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$), 11.25 μ ($\text{C}=\text{CH}_2$). The mass fragmentation pattern² is also in full accord with that of methyl betulinate (m/e 470, m/e 455, m/e 452, m/e 437, m/e 411, m/e 410, m/e 262, m/e 233, m/e 220, m/e 207, m/e 189).

The neutral ether-soluble fraction on chromatography over Brockmann alumina yielded only a very small amount of a substance, m.p 248-9°, which was identified as friedelin through its mixed m.p, determination with an authentic sample.³ The IR spectrum showed a strong peak at 5.85 μ (six membered ring

1. The authors are highly indebted to Dr. P. Sengupta of Kalyani University, Nadia, West Bengal, for supplying methyl betulinate.

2. H. Budzikiewics, J. M. Wilson and C. Djerassi, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 3688.

ketone). The mass fragmentation pattern (m/e 426, m/e 411, m/e 341, m/e 302, m/e 273, m/e 246, m/e 232, m/e 218, m/e 205) is in full accord with that for friedelin.²

The yellow crystalline material obtained from filtrate as mentioned earlier was also taken up in ether and washed with cold aqueous alkali in order to separate into neutral and acidic fractions, but alkaline layer on acidification yielded nothing worthwhile. The neutral fraction on chromatography over Brockmann alumina and subsequent elution with petroleum-benzene mixture afforded white crystalline material, m.p. 271-2°. Though this solid was eluted as a homogeneous fraction from the alumina column, it showed two diffused bands in a T L.C. plate, indicative of its non-homogeneous character. On repeated chromatography (thrice) over Brockmann alumina it could be separated into two fractions (A) m.p. 247°, (B) m.p. 279°. Both fractions responded to the Burchard-Liebermann test for triterpenoid. Fraction (A) was identified as friedelin by direct comparison with an authentic sample. Fraction (B), $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 30^\circ$ (CHCl₃), showed no colouration with tetranitromethane indicative of the absence of any double bond. It was identified as epi-friedelanol through its IR absorption at 2.85 μ (indicative of hydroxyl group) and through the preparation of derivative.

The mass spectrum of the crude triterpene mixture, m.p. 271-2°, substantiated our findings mentioned above. The spectrum not only registered a molecular ion peak at m/e 426 (friedelin) but also another at m/e 428 (epi-friedelanol). The fragmentation pattern expected for friedelin as well as that of epi-friedelanol (m/e 428, m/e 413, m/e 395, m/e 341, m/e 304, m/e 275, m/e 248, m/e 234, m/e 220, m/e 207) is in complete agreement. The fragmentation pattern of epi-friedelanol is that expected for saturated friedelane derivatives².

The ether-insoluble fraction was Soxhleted with acetone, but negligible amount of solid material was isolated therefrom. The acetone insoluble fraction on repeated crystallisation from ethyl acetate afforded white solid, m.p. 82°, having no colouration with Burchard-Liebermann reagent. Further work on this compound is in progress.

The benzene extract of the defatted stem-bark was taken up in ether and separated into neutral and acidic fractions by extraction with cold aqueous alkali. The neutral fraction on chromatography over Brockmann alumina afforded negligible amount of solid material. The acidic fraction was esterified with diazomethane and chromatographed over deactivated alumina. The only solid material came out of the column melted at 217-8°. It was identified as methyl betulinate through mixed m.p. determination and identical IR spectrum with that of an authentic sample.

Benzene extract of the bark of *E. wallichii* was also taken up in ether and separated into neutral and acidic fractions by following the same procedure as

3. The authors wish to express their sincerest thanks to Dr. D. Chakravarty, Bose Institute, Calcutta, for supplying friedelin.

mentioned earlier. The acidic fraction was esterified and characterised as methyl betulinate through the preparation of its acetate, elemental analysis, mixed m.p. determination and superimposable IR spectrum with that of an authentic specimen.

The neutral ether-soluble fraction was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina which provided three fractions (i) m.p. 247-8°, (ii) m.p. 274-5° and (iii) m.p. 132-3°. The fractions (i) and (ii) were identified as friedelin and epi-friedelanol respectively by direct comparison with authentic samples. The fraction (iii) on repeated crystallisation from ethanol afforded white shining flakes, m.p. 136.5°. It developed green colouration with Burchard-Liebermann reagent. Its analysis corresponded to $C_{29}H_{50}O$, which is in conformity with the mass-spectrometrically derived molecular weight, 414. It was identified as β -sitosterol through mixed m.p. determination and identical IR spectrum with that of an authentic sample⁴. The mass fragmentation pattern⁵ (m/e 414, m/e 399, m/e 396, m/e 303, m/e 273, m/e 255, m/e 231, m/e 213, m/e 145, m/e 119) is also in full accord with that for β -sitosterol.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Extraction of the stem-bark of *E. fruticosa*.—Dried and powdered stem-bark (700 g.) of *E. fruticosa* was extracted with petroleum in a soxhlet for 12 hr. The extract was concentrated and cooled when a deep yellow solid separated. Filtered and washed with little petroleum, a white solid residue (1.5 g.) was obtained. The filtrate on concentration afforded a deep yellow solid material (.7 g.)

Separation of the white residue into acidic and neutral fraction.—The white solid was then separated into ether-soluble and ether-insoluble portions. The ether-soluble material was then separated into neutral and acidic fractions by extraction with cold aqueous 5% NaOH solution. The white sodium salt thus obtained, on suspending in water, was treated with conc. HCl when crystalline acidic material was obtained. The ethereal layer was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and evaporated to furnish a partially crystalline material (.1 g.) (vide *infra*).

Treatment of the acidic fraction.—The above ether-soluble acidic material was taken up in ether and treated with an ethereal solution of diazomethane (prepared from 3 g. nitrosomethylurea) and allowed to stand overnight. After working up as usual, the crude esterified product was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina (40 g., deactivated with 3ml. of 10% aqueous acetic acid). Elution with petroleum-benzene mixture (1 : 1) afforded a white crystalline material (.2 g.), m.p. 215-6°, which on recrystallisation from benzene melted at 218°, $[\alpha]_D + 8.1^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$). It

* Melting points are all uncorrected. Petroleum used had b. p. 60-80°.

4. The authors are highly thankful to Dr. N. Aditya Chaudhuri, Kalyani University, Nadia, for supplying β -sitosterol.

5. S. S. Friedland, G. H. Lane, Jr., R. T. Longman, K. E. Train and M. J. O'neal, Jr., *Anal. Chem.*, 1959, 31, 169.

developed a light pink colouration with Burchard-Liebermann reagent which suggested it to be a triterpenoid ester. Its analysis corresponded to the molecular formula $C_{31}H_{50}O_3$ (Found : C, 79.38 ; H, 10.24 ; Calc for $C_{31}H_{50}O_3$: C, 79.14 ; H, 10.68%) which is in conformity with the mass-spectrometrically derived molecular weight, 470. Complete identity of the compound with methyl betulinate has been established from mixed m.p. determination and comparison of its IR spectrum with that of an authentic sample. The mass fragmentation pattern is also in full accord with that of methyl betulinate.

Methyl betulinate acetate :—The acetate of methyl betulinate was prepared by heating a mixture of methyl betulinate (.05 g.), pyridine (5 ml.) and acetic anhydride (5 ml) on a steam bath for 4 hr. After working up as usual, the crude acetate on repeated crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and ethanol, provided pure methyl betulinate acetate, m. p. 197-8° (identical mixed m. p. with an authentic sample⁶).

Treatment of neutral ether-soluble material :—The neutral ether-soluble material (.1 g.) was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina (10 g.). Elution with petroleum-benzene (1 : 1) mixture afforded a crystalline solid (.01g), m. p. 247-9°, which on recrystallisation from chloroform-ethanol mixture melted at 248-9°. It developed a light pink colouration with Burchard-Liebermann reagent. It showed an IR peak at 5.85μ (six membered ring ketone). The mass spectrometrically derived molecular formula, $C_{30}H_{50}O$, as well as the mass fragmentation pattern is in complete agreement with that of friedelin. Finally, it did not depress the m.p. of an authentic specimen.

Treatment of the yellow solid material :—The yellow crystalline material (.7 g.) was also separated into neutral and acidic fractions by extraction with cold aqueous 5% NaOH solution. The alkaline extract on acidification with conc. HCl followed by extraction with ether yielded no solid material. The neutral fraction was then chromatographed over Brockmann alumina (50 g.). Petroleum-benzene (1 : 1) eluate afforded white crystalline material (.03 g.), which was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 271-2°. This solid was found to be non-homogeneous on a T.L.C. plate (developing solvent used was benzene). On thrice chromatography over Brockmann alumina it was separated into two fractions (A) m. p. 247°, (B) m.p. 279°. Fraction (A) was identified as friedelin by direct comparison, whereas fraction (B) $[\alpha]_D + 30^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), showed an IR peak at 2.85μ , indicative of the presence of hydroxyl group. The physical constants just mentioned for fraction (B) are in close agreement with those of epi-friedelanol and it has been confirmed by the preparation of its acetate, m.p. 290°. The mass spectrum of the crude triterpene mixture, m.p, 271-2°, registered two molecular ion peaks, one at m/e 426 (friedelin) and the other at m/e 428 (epi-friedelanol).

6. The authors are highly grateful to Dr. (Mrs.) A. Chatterjee, University College of Science, Calcutta, for the generous gift of acetyl methyl betulinate.

epi-friedelanyl acetate :—*epi-friedelanol* was converted into its acetate by warming a mixture of *epi-friedelanol* (.02 g.), pyridine (5 ml.) and acetic anhydride (5 ml.). After working up as usual, the crude acetate was crystallised from chloroform-ethanol mixture, m, p. 290°.

Extraction of the defatted stem-bark with benzene :—The plant material was extracted with benzene for 18 hr. After removal of the solvent the yellow semicrystalline material (1 g.) was taken up in ether and separated into neutral and acidic fractions following the same procedure as stated previously. The neutral fraction on chromatography afforded negligible amount of solid substance. The acidic fraction was esterified with diazomethane (prepared from 2 g. nitrosomethylurea) and chromatographed over deactivated alumina (20 g., deactivated with 2 ml. 10% aqueous acetic acid). Elution with petroleum-benzene mixture furnished a crystalline solid, m. p. 217-8° (.15 g.) which was identified as methyl betulinate by direct comparison.

Extraction of the bark of E. wallichii :—Dried and powdered bark (950 g.) of *E. wallichii* was extracted with benzene for 12 hr. The yellow semicrystalline material (1.5 g.) obtained after the removal of benzene was taken up in ether and separated into neutral (.5g.) and acidic fractions (1 g.) by following the same procedure as described in the case of *E. fruticosa*.

Treatment of the acidic fraction :—The acidic material was esterified with diazomethane (prepared from 2 g. nitrosomethylurea) in the usual manner and then chromatographed over deactivated alumina (30 g., deactivated with 2 ml. of 10% aqueous acetic acid). The petroleum and petroleum-benzene (1 : 1) eluate furnished methyl betulinate (.15 g.), m.p. 219°, $[\alpha]_D + 8^\circ$, (Found C, 79.40; H, 10.42; Calc. for $C_{31}H_{50}O_3$: C, 79.14; H, 10.68%).

Friedelin :—Elution with a mixture of petroleum-benzene (4 : 1 and 3 : 2) in the chromatogram afforded *friedelin* (.03 g.) which on crystallisation from chloroform-ethanol mixture melted at 248-9° (Found : C, 84.24; H, 11.92; Calc. for $C_{30}H_{50}O$: C, 84.50; H, 11.74%). It exhibited no colouration with tetranitromethane.

Friedelin Oxime :—*Friedelin* was converted into its oxime according to the procedure of Drake and Shrader⁷. The oxime melted at 290° (Lit. m.p. 290-4°).

epi-friedelanol :—Elution with a mixture of petroleum-benzene (2 : 3) afforded *epi-friedelanol* (.005 g.) which on recrystallisation from benzene melted at 278-9°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of *epi-friedelanol* remained undepressed.

β -sitosterol ;—Elution with acetone afforded yellowish-white solid (.05 g.) m.p. 132-3°, which furnished shining white flakes, m.p. 136.5°, on repeated crystallisation from ethanol. Its identity with *β -sitosterol* was established through mixed m.p. determination with an authentic specimen⁴. The IR spectrum (KBr) showed a strong

peak at 2.95μ (—OH group). Its analysis (Found : C, 83.81 ; H, 12.42 ; Calc. for $C_{29}H_{50}O$: C, 84.07 ; H, 12.08%) is in well accord with the mass-spectrometrically derived molecular weight, 414.

β -sitosterol acetate :— β -sitosterol (.02 g.) was acetylated in the usual manner with acetic anhydride (5 ml.) and pyridine (5ml.). The crude acetyl derivative on repeated crystallisation from chloroform-ethanol mixture afforded white crystalline material, m.p. 126.5° . IR spectrum showed peak at 5.8μ (—CO.CH₃).

The authors are highly indebted to Prof. S. K. Siddhanta for his constant encouragement and to Prof. P. N. Bhaduri for his keen interest and helping us in collecting and identifying the plant species. Thanks are due to Dr. B. C. Das, Gif-Sur-Yvette, France for mass spectral analysis. IR spectra and microanalysis were performed in the Department of Chemistry, C. D. R.I., Lucknow, through the courtesy of Dr. B. N. Singh, Deputy Director, C. D. R. I.

The authors are also indebted to the University of Burdwan for the award of a scholarship to one of them (S. T.)

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
THE UNIVERSITY OF BURDWAN,
BURDWAN, WEST BENGAL.

Received, December 13, 1967.